

OPPORTUNITIES TO DEVELOP EMBROIDERY COMPETENCE IN WOMEN GIRLS
BASED ON PROGRAMMING

Magdieva Markhabo Erkinovna

Nizomi TDPU Faculty of Primary Education, teacher of the Department of Mathematics and
Methods of Teaching it in Primary School

ANNOTATION. Pedagogical possibilities are revealed: the professional graphic program Corel Draw has great capabilities for creating and coloring embroidery compositions, and with the help of this program you can color the embroidery composition in different colors and select the appropriate color in a short time. We will look at this process using the example of creating and coloring a girikh embroidery composition.

Key words: craftsman, folk crafts, professional practical competence, tradition, pedagogical possibilities

It is important to introduce students to embroidery art schools and their representatives

During the time of the Khanate, masters of folk art began to gather in cities such as Khiva, Kokan, Bukhara, and Samarkand. Painters from Ferghana and Bukhara often came to Samarkand, and masters from Kokand and Margilan came to Tashkent to decorate buildings. This plays a big role in the further development of embroidery schools, the creation of unique compositions, and the enrichment of the color complex. Although these embroideries are similar to each other, each school of embroidery is distinguished by its own rules, principles, work style, and color scheme.

Tashkent embroidery school. Tashkent embroideries are distinguished by their elegance and the gradual transition of colors to each other, strict adherence to a certain color scheme, and the frequent use of geometric and plant-like embroideries. Embroidery is often done in green gamma. In Islamic embroidery, complex girikh embroidery with clearly stylized moonflower, cotton, cotton, three leaves, shukufta, leafy flower and other elements is also widely used.

Khiva embroidery school. Khiva embroidery is fundamentally different from Samarkand, Tashkent, Fergana, Bukhara. Blue and green colors are mostly used in Khiva embroidery. The composition of Islamic embroidery consists of a branch, a flower, a rose, a leaf, a pea, a flower, and a simple moon. Most often, star-shaped loops are used, and the middle is enriched with spiral Islamic embroidery. Khiva embroidery is generally made on the basis of mixed compositions.

Bukhara and Samarkand embroidery schools. Bukhara is distinguished by the complexity and attractiveness of kashtai compositions. Bukhara embroideries are distinguished by the use of complex loops in a clear and precise size, and the special attention paid to the rhythm of leaves, fruits, and flowers in vegetable embroideries. Samarkand embroidery is similar to Tashkent and Ferghana methods. Samarkand embroideries are distinguished by their extreme floweriness, the mobility and liveliness of their leaves and flowers. The embroideries are first blue and then green. In order to further strengthen the above information in the minds of students, it is important to complete the following educational task.

Achieving such a result requires the use of IT in the educational process. The technologies are very different. We will dwell on the organization of some of them and the procedure for conducting them.

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The "Blitz-survey" method helps students to correctly organize the sequence of actions, to think logically, to choose from various opinions and information based on the subject they are studying, and at the same time, others aimed at respecting their opinion and teaching them to be able to express their opinion and to plan their activities and day. Through this method, it is possible to independently determine the sequence of actions shown on the papers distributed to students, to be able to convey one's opinion to others in small groups, or to remain in one's opinion, to be able to agree with others. skills are formed.

"Charkhpalak" technology helps to teach students to memorize the topics covered, to think logically, to independently answer correctly to the given questions and to self-assess, and in a short time, the teacher teaches all students helps to evaluate acquired knowledge. This technology can be organized in the form of individual, small group and collective training.

In teaching students to think and remember individually and in small groups on the topics defined in the program, to remember the acquired knowledge, to summarize the collected thoughts and to express them in writing, pictures, drawings, "Zinama-zina" » technology gives effective results. This technology is conducted in writing and presented with students individually or in groups.

Providing education to students in accordance with the requirements of the times, using various pedagogical technologies and modern methods, encourages them to think independently and freely, to search, to approach each issue creatively.

Information technology is rapidly entering every field. We can see the confirmation of this in the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On further development of computerization and introduction of information and communication technologies". In fact, nowadays it is difficult to find academic subjects in the field of education that do not use computer capabilities. Various programs of information technologies applied to all subjects in the educational process have been developed and are widely used in practice.

In particular, the Corel Draw graphic program provides convenience in creating and coloring embroidery compositions in the art of embroidery. This program offers many possibilities in terms of graphic design page development, photo analysis and vector animation. Also, the program reduces several times the actions needed to create a composition and perform it. For example, new elements: ellipses, right angles and curves will be given the required size and rotation angle by double-clicking the "mouse" button.

The Corel Draw professional graphic program has great capabilities in creating and coloring embroidery compositions, and through this program, you can quickly color the embroidery composition in different colors and choose the appropriate color. We will consider this process by creating and coloring a girih kashta composition.

To start Corel Draw, find its icon on the desktop, hover over it, and double-click the left mouse button. If this picture is not found on the screen, bring the mouse pointer over the "Pusk" menu in the taskbar below and press the left button once. The "program" section is selected from the list that appears. In the list on the right, find the line Corel Draw and left-click on it once. After completing these steps, the Corel Draw program will start. From the "Nabor instrumentov" (equipment) menu, select the "rectangular" command and use the "strl" key to draw a square shape.

Then the command "svobodnaya forma" is selected from the "Nabor instrumentov" menu, vertical and horizontal lines are drawn using the "strl" key. Then select the "ellipse" command and use the "strl" key to draw a circle with the lower right point of the square as the center. The radius

of a circle is equal to the side of a square. Using the "arc" (arc) command of the menu, an arc is created, one of which is equal to 900 and one to 1800, and a horizontal line is drawn from the created point. The left side of the square is connected with this line and point b is formed. Then, using the "ellipse" command, the "strl" button, and the "arc" command of the menu, an arc is created by centering the V point of the square. A vertical line is drawn from the resulting point s and a point d is formed. Then, using the "ellipse" command, the "strl" key, and the "arc" command of the menu, an arc is drawn with the point A of the square as the center. The point j is found by drawing a horizontal line through the resulting point y. Using the "ellipse" command, the "strl" key, and the "arc" command of the menu, an arc is drawn with the point D of the square as the center. We draw a vertical line from the resulting z point and form the i point. An arc is drawn from the point L, which is formed by the intersection of horizontal and vertical lines, with point D as the center, as shown above. Points p and r are formed by intersecting the square with the arc.

An arc is drawn from point R to point J as the center, in the order shown above, points s and t are formed, from r to point p, and from it to point t formed by the intersection of a vertical line with a semicircle. 'is carried out and that point is formed. Parallel to this line, a line is drawn from point r and point f is formed, and points u and f are connected, resulting in a rectangle. The same rectangle is formed in the opposite diagonal direction. In the next step, lines are drawn from point J to points o and n, from point E to points m and l, from point Z to points o and l, and from point I to points m and n. Now we connect the necessary points and form a geometric shape on all sides of the square. Finally, from the sum of these geometric shapes, the complex embroidery composition we expected was formed (Fig. 2).

A complex embroidery composition created using the Corel Draw graphic program

Such training will increase interest in education, science and the chosen profession in the future in organizing scientific and creative work and conducting research.

Today, ATs and their concepts are considered somewhat popular, and it is known to many of us that they have entered into practice. It can be said that they are based on a non-traditional education system.

In this regard, the large-scale implementation of IT in the educational process, the enrichment of the educational content, its improvement, and the acceleration of the acquisition of students' knowledge, by conducting collective and individual exercises, make education a complex helps to solve design problems.

The use of IT in the educational process is one of the main factors of developing its content, updating its forms and methods. These, in turn, make important changes to the content of pedagogical activity.

The process of professional training of a future teacher of vocational education for the use of IT is the process of forming a set of characteristics that ensure a high level of organization of the person's activities on the use of IT in the future professional activity. The process of creating an artistic image is related to the pursuit of a state of conscious imagination through the analysis of forms.

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